

In-network AI capabilities through hardware switches and optical computing

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Abstract—In-band telemetry could expand its functionalities through AI. However, practical limitations in hardware switches prevents this upgrade. Here, we discuss how an hardware-aware design can bring in-network AI through ASIC switches and optical computing.

Index Terms—Telemetry, Optical Computing, In-Network AI.

I. INTRODUCTION

Telemetry enables accurate monitoring of packet-optical network performance, supporting advanced traffic engineering and failure detection [1, 2]. However, centralized telemetry systems face scalability challenges due to high data volumes [3]. To address this, distributed or peer-to-peer approaches have emerged. For instance, transmitters and receivers may directly exchange telemetry data to optimize operations without involving centralized collectors or the Software Defined Networking (SDN) Controller [4]. Hardware offloading has also been proposed to enhance scalability by accelerating data processing at the collector [5]. However, processing large amount of telemetry data remains challenging in distributed environments.

In this invited contribution we present an effective solution for in-network processing of telemetry data. Furthermore, building on our previous works, we discuss how to bring in-network AI capabilities without drowning the available computational resources through: (I) an hardware-aware design that allows to deploy deep neural networks as Look-Up Tables (LUTs) within programmable network devices [6]; (II) the use of neuromorphic photonic chips for the deployment of fast and efficient AI models directly in the optical domain [7].

Fig. 1. Reference topology

II. DISTRIBUTED TELEMTRY WITH IN-NETWORK PROCESSING

Fig. 1 illustrates a network of four packet-optical nodes interconnected via optical line systems. N1 and N2 are connected by two unidirectional lightpaths, L_{12} and L_{21} , with alternative paths through N3 and N4. Each node monitors the Quality of Transmission (QoT) of its received lightpaths (e.g., OSNR, pre-FEC BER, RX power) and local packet-level Quality of Service (QoS) metrics (e.g., traffic rates, queue lengths). For example, N2 monitors traffic from N1, N3, and N4, and can detect soft failures on L_{12} .

Traditional SDN-based approaches limit visibility: N2 lacks direct insight into L_{21} and depends on external notifications from N1. While hard failures can be handled via routing protocols or Bidirectional Forwarding Detection (BFD), soft failures—causing elevated BERs without link-down events—often go undetected or are signaled too slowly. Centralized SDN notification mechanisms may also fall short in scalability and responsiveness. Moreover, N2 cannot assess the status of non-direct paths (e.g., N3-N1 or N4-N1), which may also suffer from impairments or lack of bandwidth.

To address these issues, this work presents a framework based on direct in-network exchange of telemetry reports. These reports convey real-time QoT and QoS information for relevant links. By collecting data from N1, N3, and N4, N2 gains visibility on 1-hop-away outgoing links, enabling fast selection among paths such as L_{21} , L_{23} - L_{31} , or L_{24} - L_{41} .

Fig. 2. P4 design of in-band MLNT-based steering pipelines.

Fig. 3. In-network AI capabilities through LUT distillation and photonic computing. PIC: photonic integrated circuit.

Telemetry reports are processed at wire speed by the P4 ASIC, with stateful operations applied directly to the telemetry data. The solution has been implemented in a testbed replicating Fig. 1. N2 uses a P4 Tofino switch, while N1, N3, and N4 are Mellanox/Nvidia switches with Spectrum1/2 P4 ASICs, running SONiC and 100G optical pluggables. A soft failure is emulated via in-line attenuation. At N1, a SONiC-based application reads QoT (RX power) and QoS (bit rates) for L_{21} from Redis, then uses a Thrift interface to embed these values into flow rules. Telemetry packets, cloned from specific management flows, match these rules and are updated with the telemetry data via in-network P4 operations at wire speed.

Fig. 2 shows the considered P4 implementation. Multi-Layer Network Telemetry (MLNT) data are embedded in packets and matched as metadata for immediate forwarding via range-based matching (i.e., *packet_steer* action). Upon receiving MLNT data, N2 processes on a per packet basis. If thresholds are exceeded, L_{21} traffic is rerouted using pre-installed rules (e.g., via L_{23} - L_{31} or L_{24} - L_{41}). The reroute latency—from MLNT packet reception to first redirected data packet—is $2\mu\text{s}$ in both cases. MLNT reports, derived from standard INT formats, are 60–100 bytes each. At one packet every 10ms, bandwidth usage is 0.08Mb/s; even at 1pkt/ms, overhead remains below 0.001% of a 100Gb/s link. In this test, MLNT forwarding is limited to 1-hop.

III. LUT DISTILLATION AND PHOTONIC COMPUTING FOR IN-NETWORK AI DEPLOYMENT

Modern machine learning models, such as deep neural networks (DNN), have proved to be an effective tool in a plethora of fields, including computer networks and optical communications. However, their use is hindered because of their associated computational burden: the inherent parallel computing architecture of neural networks is hardly modelled as sequential commands on digital processors. These AI models are especially difficult to implement within the data plane, where ASICs provide just essential computational capabilities (usually match-actions), and a wirespeed processing is required.

To overcome these challenges, we have developed two possible solutions to deploy in-network AI capabilities exploiting either a hardware aware design of neural networks or the recent advances in optical computing chips. Fig. 3 reports the two solutions embedded within a packet-optical network.

On the right is depicted the LUT distillation method, that allows to map the entire pipeline, including the DNN, into programmable switch/NICs, with the possibility to change the network function, or update the model, via LUT flow entries. This solution allows to implement AI models acting as either network intrusion detection or traffic classification within the same switch/NIC. The technical details of this solution are reported in our recent work [6]. In conjunction, recent advances in integrated photonic computing can provide another way to implement AI capabilities within optical links. Neuromorphic photonics finds an almost natural fit within the optical communication scenario. The high-bandwidth and low-latency requirements posed by high-speed optical links are well met by photonic integrated chips. Moreover, the signals are conveniently available in the optical domain, relieving the need for input signals electro-optical conversion. These photonic circuits can be used as adaptive regenerative stages that compensate nonlinearities, or used for pattern recognition tasks [8]. The left side of Fig. 3, depicts a possible transparent neuromorphic chip acting in dual polarization directly embedded in optical links.

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